

NAVRUZ HOLIDAY AND ITS ETHNIC CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6563699>

Adambayev Umidbek Xaitbayevich

Teacher's of TVCHDPI

Rahimov Alisher Akmal o'g'li

student's of TVCHDPI

Jabborov Xurshid Shuhrat o'g'li

student's of TVCHDPI

ABSTRACT: *In this article, the researcher comments on the essence of Navruz and the time of its formation and celebration, medieval sources about it and the events of the holiday, as well as the attention paid to Navruz after independence.*

Keywords: *Navruz, Zoroastrianism, holiday, tradition, ancient sources, big Navruz, small Navruz, new day*

According to historical sources and our scholars, according to the period of formation of Navruz - the oldest of "Zoroastrianism" appeared from time immemorial and will last for centuries.

From ancient times, the neutral intentions of the people of Navruz are a beautiful holiday.

Navruz came to our bodies, it was from ancient sources that the Achaemenid period (early 6th century BC) was widespread in Mediterranean Asia, Iran and Afghanistan. In this sense, it is assumed that the period of the history of Navruz up to the 25th-30th centuries can be realized. [1]

Navruz has a solid appearance since its inception is a comprehensive scientific report based on the laws of the universe and nature. For example, entering the zodiac sign of the sun, the intensification of daylight, the restoration of nature - is accepted as Navruz (Navruz - means "new"). The old solar calendar of Navruz starts at the beginning of the month (now March 22). [2] Today it is called Navruz and it is believed that everything from this nature has been put in its place.

Beruni's book "Monuments of Ancient Peoples" [2, 73] provides valuable information and then notes that the small holiday fair lasts until the sixth month. And so, from the sixth of the month Farvardin connects the essence of the Great Of Navruz directly with nature and writes about it as follows: until the flowers open the trees. in animals, from the time the fruit blooms to the

time it is reproduced in the body until it continues at that time. That is why the beginning and creation of the universe Navruz has been proved. ”These are the nature of Navruz that has been thought of for a long time and the spring holiday that is repeated many times . proves. However, in the history of Navruz , the essence is interpreted differently, so some will motivate its development, while others The tickling action they did. In particular, the periods of Greek-Macedonian and Arab conquests Navruz forbidden, it is not considered an official holiday in the palaces of kings, officials and religious circles. Emphasizing the transition period, Navruz has retained its essence in the past , although the form of the domination of one class of kings in society has changed under the influence of religious ideology. It is a true folk holiday, with people working between large ceremonies .

Consequently, from time immemorial, the people have had their own rituals. The customs of Islam during Navruz are also noteworthy . On the holiday, people give each other sugar and sweets (in the sense of getting sweet in your life) , sprinkle water on each other (in the sense of getting a lot of water this year _ in the sense of getting better) and a wide range of other habits. scattered In the following centuries , customs such as cleaning the yard, planting greenery and flowers, visiting parents and friends , visiting the grave of the deceased will become part of the composition of Navruz .

In the post-independence years, including after 1991, Navruz has risen to the level of a national holiday. [3] Congratulations on the holiday today with great preparation. The Presidents of Uzbekistan congratulated the people on Navruz .

Conclusion, the celebration of Navruz promotes great values such as peace and harmony, harmony and harmony , reconciling elderly families , striving to preserve them _ Values include cultural diversity and humanity, healthy lifestyle and living providing conditions. updates, such as habits passed down from generation to generation

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. <https://meros.uz/object/navroz-holiday>
2. Sobirova M., Kholikov E., Ethnoculture. Textbook –T.: Innovation and enlightenment. 2021. 74 b.
3. Decree of the President of the Uzbek SSR No. PF-143 of 12.02.1991. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1991, No. 5, Article 96)

4. Umidbek Adambayev. (2021). FAITH – THE CONCEPTION OF BELIEF AND STEPS TO DEVELOP IT / ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TRAINING. – pp. 96-100.

5. U. Adambaev. (2021). CONFIDENCE-NONVERBAL METHODS OF ARGUMENTATION IN THE FORMATION OF THE VERB /Экономика и социум. – С.18-21.

6. Адамбаев, У. Х. (2022). ИШОНЧ-ЭЪТИҚОДНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШДА АРГУМЕНТЛАШНИНГ ЎРНИ. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 3(1), 898-905.

7. Умидбек Хаитбаевич Адамбаев, (2022). Ишонч – эътиқодни шакллантиришда урф-одат ва анъаналарнинг таъсири, SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS (pp. 348-351).

8. Адамбаев, У. Х., & Джораев, Д. Ў. (2022). ЭКОЛОГИК МАДАНИЯТ ВА УНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 3(2), 125-134.

9. Adambayev, U. X., & Rahimberdiyev, S. U. (2022). NAVRO‘Z BAYRAMI VA UNING ETNOMADANIY AHAMIYATI. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 3(2), 175-177.

10. Umid Adambayev. (2021). MILLIY O‘ZLIKNI ANGLASH MILLAT TARAQIYOTINING POYDEVORI / Scientific progress. – pp. 1858-1862.

11. U. X. Adambayev. (2022). AMIR TEMUR YURITGAN DAVLAT SIYOSATI. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 6(1), 68-71.

12. U.X. Adambayev. (2022). ETNOMADANIYATNING INSONLAR HAYOTIDA TUTGAN O‘RNI. Scientific Progress 3 (3), 519-521.

13. U.X. Adambayev. (2022). ZAMONAVIY DUNYO: IJTIMOY TARMOQLAR INSON RESURSLARINI BOSHQARADI. Scientific Progress 3 (3), 499-501.

14. U.X. Adambayev. (2022). SOG‘LOM OILADA MADANIY TARBIYANING SHAKLLANTIRISH. Scientific Progress 3 (3), 502-505.

15. U.X. Adambayev. (2022). JAMOATCHILIK NAZORATI VA UNI TASHKIL ETISHDA YOSHLARNING O‘RNI VA ROLI. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 3(4), 260-264.

16. U.X. Adambayev. (2022). XIX АСРНИНГ БОШЛАРИДАТУРКИСТОНДА ЖАДИДЧИЛИК ҲАРАКАТИНИНГ ЭТНОПЕДАГОГИК АҲАМИЯТИ. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, 3(4), 273-279.

